

**CONGRUENCE PROPERTIES FOR THE TRINOMIAL
COEFFICIENTS**

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Abstract

In this paper, we state and prove some congruence properties for the trinomial coefficients, one of which is similar to Wolstenholme's theorem.

1. Introduction

In 1819, Babbage [4] showed for any odd prime p ,

$$\binom{2p-1}{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^2}. \quad (1)$$

In 1862, Wolstenholme [21] proved that the above congruence holds modulo p^3 for any prime $p \geq 5$, i.e.,

$$\binom{2p-1}{p-1} \equiv 1 \pmod{p^3}, \quad (2)$$

which is known as Wolstenholme's theorem. It is well-known that Wolstenholme's theorem is a fundamental congruence in combinatorial number theory. We refer to [14] for various extensions of Wolstenholme's theorem.

In the past few years, (q -)congruences for sums of binomial coefficients have attracted the attention of many researchers (see, for instance, [2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 19, 20]). In 2011, Sun and Tauraso [20] proved that for any prime $p \geq 5$,

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{2k}{k} \equiv \left(\frac{p}{3}\right) \pmod{p^2}, \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{2k}{k} \frac{1}{k+1} \equiv \frac{3}{2} \left(\frac{p}{3}\right) - \frac{1}{2} \pmod{p^2}, \tag{4}$$

where $\left(\frac{\cdot}{p}\right)$ denotes the Legendre symbol. Note that $\binom{2k}{k} \frac{1}{k+1}$ is the n -th Catalan number C_n , which plays an important role in various counting problems. Extensions of (3) and (4) have been established in [3, 10].

In 2018, the first author [2] conjectured two congruences on sums of the super Catalan numbers (named by Gessel [5]):

$$\sum_{i=0}^{p-1} \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} \frac{\binom{2i}{i} \binom{2j}{j}}{\binom{i+j}{i}} \equiv \left(\frac{p}{3}\right) \pmod{p},$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{p-1} \sum_{j=0}^{p-1} (3i + 3j + 1) \frac{\binom{2i}{i} \binom{2j}{j}}{\binom{i+j}{i}} \equiv -7 \left(\frac{p}{3}\right) \pmod{p},$$

which were confirmed by the second author [11].

In this paper, we will study the congruence properties for the trinomial coefficients. Here we consider the coefficients of the trinomial

$$(1 + x + x^{-1})^n = \sum_{j=-n}^n \left(\binom{n}{j}\right) x^j.$$

Two immediate consequences of this definition are

$$\left(\binom{n}{j}\right) = \left(\binom{n}{-j}\right),$$

and

$$\left(\binom{n}{j}\right) = \left(\binom{n-1}{j-1}\right) + \left(\binom{n-1}{j}\right) + \left(\binom{n-1}{j+1}\right).$$

We have the following multinomial theorem (see [18, page 17]):

$$(x + y + z)^n = \sum_{a+b+c=n} \frac{n!}{a!b!c!} x^a y^b z^c. \tag{5}$$

Letting $y = 1$ and $z = 1/x$ in (5), we get

$$\left(\binom{n}{j}\right) = \sum_{\substack{a+b+c=n \\ a-c=j}} \frac{n!}{a!b!c!} = \sum_{c=0}^n \binom{n}{c} \binom{n-c}{c+j}. \tag{6}$$

We first prove a congruence for the trinomial coefficients, which is similar to Wolstenholme’s theorem.

Theorem 1. *For any prime $p \geq 5$, we have*

$$\binom{\binom{2p}{p}}{p} \equiv 2 + \frac{2p^2}{3} \binom{p}{3} B_{p-2} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \pmod{p^3}, \tag{7}$$

where $B_n(x)$ is the Bernoulli polynomial of order n .

The second result consists of the following two congruences on single sums of trinomial coefficients.

Theorem 2. *For any prime $p \geq 5$, we have*

$$\sum_{j=0}^p \binom{\binom{p}{j}}{j} \equiv \frac{1}{2} (1 + 3^p) \pmod{p^2}, \tag{8}$$

$$\sum_{j=0}^{p-1} \binom{\binom{p-1}{j}}{j} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \binom{p}{3}\right) \pmod{p}. \tag{9}$$

The third aim of the paper is to establish a congruence on double sums of trinomial coefficients.

Theorem 3. *For any prime $p \geq 5$ and integer j with $0 < j < p$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{\binom{k}{j}}{j} \equiv \frac{(-1)^j + 1}{2} \cdot (-1)^{\frac{p-j-1}{2}} \pmod{p}, \tag{10}$$

$$\sum_{m=0}^{p-1} \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} \binom{\binom{m}{n}}{n} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left((-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} + 1 \right) \pmod{p}. \tag{11}$$

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. We shall prove Theorems 1, 2 and 3 in Sections 2, 3 and 4, respectively. An open problem on q -congruence is proposed in the last section for further research.

2. Proof of Theorem 1

By (2) and (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{\binom{2p}{p}}{p} &= \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \binom{2p}{k} \binom{2p-k}{k+p} \\ &\equiv 2 + \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \binom{2p}{k} \binom{2p-k}{k+p} \pmod{p^3}. \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Let H_k denote the k -th harmonic number:

$$H_k = \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{1}{j}.$$

For any integer s and $0 \leq k \leq p - 1$, we have

$$\binom{sp - 1}{k} \equiv (-1)^k (1 - spH_k) \pmod{p^2}, \tag{13}$$

and

$$\binom{sp + k}{k} \equiv 1 + spH_k \pmod{p^2}. \tag{14}$$

It follows from (1), (13) and (14) that for $1 \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$,

$$\binom{2p}{k} = \frac{2p}{k} \binom{2p-1}{k-1} \equiv \frac{2p(-1)^{k-1}}{k} (1 - 2pH_{k-1}) \pmod{p^3}, \tag{15}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{2p-k}{k+p} &= \frac{\binom{2p}{p} \binom{2k}{k}}{4} \cdot \frac{\binom{p-1}{2k-1}}{\binom{2p-1}{k-1} \binom{p+k}{k}} \\ &\equiv (-1)^{k-1} \binom{2k}{k} \cdot \frac{pH_{2k-1} - 1}{2(1 - 2pH_{k-1})(1 + pH_k)} \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Substituting (15) and (16) into (12) gives

$$\left(\binom{2p}{p} \right) \equiv 2 + p \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k} (pH_{2k-1} - 1)}{k(1 + pH_k)} \pmod{p^3}. \tag{17}$$

Note that

$$\frac{pH_{2k-1} - 1}{1 + pH_k} \equiv -1 + (H_k + H_{2k-1})p \pmod{p^2}. \tag{18}$$

Combining (17) and (18), we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\binom{2p}{p} \right) &\equiv 2 - p \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} + p^2 \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} (H_k + H_{2k-1}) \pmod{p^3} \\ &= 2 + p \left(p \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} H_{2k} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} \right) + p^2 \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} H_k - \frac{p^2}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Using the following congruence [12, (2.8)]:

$$p \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} H_{2k} - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} \equiv \frac{5p}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k^2} - 2p \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} H_k \pmod{p^2},$$

we have

$$\left(\binom{2p}{p}\right) \equiv 2 + 2p^2 \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k^2} - p^2 \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} H_k \pmod{p^3}. \tag{19}$$

We have the following two congruences (see [12, (1.1)] and [13, page 156]):

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} H_k \equiv \frac{1}{3} \binom{p}{3} B_{p-2} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \pmod{p}, \tag{20}$$

and

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k^2} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \binom{p}{3} B_{p-2} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \pmod{p}. \tag{21}$$

Finally, combining (19)–(21), we complete the proof of (7).

3. Proof of Theorem 2

Proof of (8). We begin with the following identity, which is A027914 of the Online Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences [17]:

$$\sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} = \frac{1}{2} \left(3^n + \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \binom{n-k}{k} \right). \tag{22}$$

Letting $n = p$ in the above gives

$$\sum_{j=0}^p \binom{p}{j} = \frac{1}{2} \left(3^p + \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \binom{p}{k} \binom{p-k}{k} \right).$$

Note that for $1 \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$,

$$\begin{aligned} \binom{p}{k} \binom{p-k}{k} &= \frac{p(p-1) \cdots (p-k+1)(p-k)(p-k-1) \cdots (p-2k+1)}{k!^2} \\ &\equiv -\frac{p}{2k} \binom{2k}{k} \pmod{p^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\sum_{j=0}^p \binom{p}{j} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(3^p + 1 - \frac{p}{2} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} \right) \pmod{p^2}.$$

We have the following congruence [15, (1.6)]:

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \frac{\binom{2k}{k}}{k} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

It follows that

$$\sum_{j=0}^p \binom{p}{j} \equiv \frac{1}{2} (3^p + 1) \pmod{p^2},$$

as desired. □

Proof of (9). Letting $n = p - 1$ in (22), we obtain

$$\sum_{j=0}^{p-1} \binom{p-1}{j} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(3^{p-1} + \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \binom{p-1}{k} \binom{p-1-k}{k} \right).$$

Note that for $0 \leq k \leq \frac{p-1}{2}$,

$$\binom{p-1}{k} \equiv (-1)^k \pmod{p},$$

and

$$\binom{p-1-k}{k} = \frac{(p-1-k)(p-2-k) \cdots (p-2k)}{k!} \equiv (-1)^k \binom{2k}{k} \pmod{p}.$$

By the above two congruences and Fermat's little theorem, we have

$$\sum_{j=0}^{p-1} \binom{p-1}{j} \equiv \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \sum_{k=0}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} \binom{2k}{k} \right) \pmod{p}. \tag{23}$$

Then the proof of (9) follows from (3) and (23). □

4. Proof of Theorem 3

Proof of (10). Exchanging the summation order, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{k}{j} &= \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \sum_{i=0}^k \binom{k}{i} \binom{k-i}{i+j} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{p-1} \sum_{k=i}^{p-1} \binom{k}{i} \binom{k-i}{i+j}. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\binom{k}{i} \binom{k-i}{i+j} = \binom{2i+j}{i} \binom{k}{2i+j},$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{k}{j} &= \sum_{i=0}^{p-1} \binom{2i+j}{i} \sum_{k=i}^{p-1} \binom{k}{2i+j} \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{p-1} \binom{2i+j}{i} \binom{p}{2i+j+1}, \end{aligned}$$

where we have utilized the identity (proved by induction):

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{k}{m} = \binom{n+1}{m+1}.$$

Note that for $1 \leq k \leq p-1$,

$$\binom{p}{k} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

If j is odd, then

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{k}{j} \equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

If j is even, then

$$\sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \binom{k}{j} \equiv \binom{p-1}{\frac{p-j-1}{2}} \equiv (-1)^{\frac{p-j-1}{2}} \pmod{p}.$$

This completes the proof of (10). □

Proof of (11). By (10), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{m=0}^{p-1} \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} \binom{m}{n} &\equiv \sum_{n=0}^{p-1} \frac{(-1)^n + 1}{2} \cdot (-1)^{\frac{p-n-1}{2}} \pmod{p} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\frac{p-1}{2}} (-1)^{\frac{p-2n-1}{2}} \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left((-1)^{\frac{p-1}{2}} + 1 \right), \end{aligned}$$

as claimed. □

Remark. Theorems 2 and 3 can also be established by using the method of the first author and Zeilberger [3].

5. Concluding Remarks

We have three q -analogs corresponding to the trinomial coefficients as given in [16], namely,

$$\begin{aligned} T_1(n, j, q) &:= \sum_{k=0}^n q^{k(k+j)} \binom{n}{k}_q \binom{n-k}{k+j}_q, \\ T_2(n, j, q) &:= \sum_{k=0}^n (-1)^k \binom{n}{k}_{q^2} \binom{2n-2k}{n-k-j}_q, \\ T_3(n, j, q) &:= \sum_{k=0}^n (-q)^k \binom{n}{k}_{q^2} \binom{2n-2k}{n-k-j}_q, \end{aligned}$$

where the q -binomial coefficients $\binom{n}{k}_q$ are defined as

$$\binom{n}{k}_q = \begin{cases} \frac{(1-q^n)(1-q^{n-1}) \cdots (1-q^{n-k+1})}{(1-q)(1-q^2) \cdots (1-q^k)}, & \text{if } 0 \leq k \leq n, \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

It is not hard to prove the following q -congruences.

Proposition 1. *For any odd prime p and integer $1 \leq s \leq 3$, we have*

$$\sum_{j=0}^{p-1} T_s(p, j, q) \equiv 1 \pmod{[p]_q},$$

where the q -integers are given by $[n]_q = (1 - q^n)/(1 - q)$.

The proof of Proposition 1 is trivial and left to the interested reader.

In 1999, Andrews [1] established an interesting q -analog of Babbage’s congruence (1):

$$\binom{2p-1}{p-1}_q \equiv q^{\frac{p(p-1)}{2}} \pmod{[p]_q^2},$$

for any odd prime p . It is natural to ask whether the congruence (7) possesses a q -analog. For convenience sake, let

$$\binom{\binom{n}{j}}{j}_q = T_1(n, j, q).$$

Numerical calculation suggests the following q -congruence, and we propose this conjecture for further research.

Conjecture 1. For any prime $p \geq 5$, we have

$$\binom{\binom{2p}{p}}{p}_q \equiv \left(2 \left\lfloor \frac{p+3}{6} \right\rfloor + p\right) (q^p - 1) + 2 \pmod{[p]_q^2}, \tag{24}$$

where $\lfloor x \rfloor$ denotes the integral part of real x .

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